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UNEMPLOYMENT AMONG YOUTHS AND ITS IMPACT ON LOCAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN YOLA SOUTH, ADAMAWA

Ibrahim Musa Gambo

Department of Accountancy,
College of Administrative and Business Studies,
Numan,
Adamawa State Polytechnic, Nigeria.
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Abstract: This study is on “socio-economic effects of youth’s unemployment in Yola South Local Government Area of Adamawa State”. It is a common fact that youth unemployment is becoming a threat to the economic development in Nigeria. The study examines the effects of youth unemployment in Nigeria on the economic development and its resultant consequences. The study aimed to identify whether high rate of poverty and crime are recorded as a result of unemployment. The study employed the primary data where information was collected from various individuals in Yola South Local Government Area of Adamawa State whom are mostly youth. Responses from 500 questionnaires analysed using simple percentage and chi-square was used to test the hypothesis. The result from the study reveals that youths are involved in drugs abuse, criminal activities and increased rate of poverty among other things. Thus, unemployment had adverse effects on the nation’s socioeconomic development and therefore reduces the standard of living. Based on the finding, it was proffered that the employment scheme and other manpower skills development programmes should be designed to reduce the unemployment rate in the country. Government should establish more industries in order to create more jobs for the teeming youths. Sensitizations on the dangers of drug abuse need to be intensified by the relevant government agencies.

Keywords: Unemployment; Poverty; Drug abuse.

1.0 Introduction

Youth unemployment in Nigeria has become one of the most serious socio-economic problems confronting the country. Unemployed youths are therefore readily available for so many antisocial criminal activities that undermine the stability of our society and Nigeria in general. Similarly, the devastating impact of this problem of unemployment is the massive increase in rural-urban migration, leading to an increased congestion and criminal activities in the urban areas.

Therefore, the need for strategies that will lead to job creation for the teeming youths and social development is needed. Hence, in order to address the youth unemployment in Nigeria, there is need for a holistic approach; as short-cuts will not work any longer (Echebiri, R.N. (2005). According to Gbosi (2006), unemployment is situations in which people are willing to work at the prevailing wage rate are unable to find jobs. The implication is that, there

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are available skilled individuals in art economy seeking to be hired and work but remain unhired. Unemployment has affected youth in Nigeria from a broad spectrum of socio-economic groups. Both the well and less well educated are affected but more especially those from low income backgrounds and limited education. This has led to low level of income, shortage of food, over population, which causes congestion and crime rate in the society. Also, it has cause youths to become drug abuse champions.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Unemployment has been categorized as one of the serious impediments of social progress from representing a colossal waste of a country's manpower resources; it generates welfare loss in terms of lower output thereby leading to lower income and well-being.

The need to avert the negative effect of unemployment has made the tackling of unemployment problems to feature very prominently in the development objectives of many countries. Therefore, the major problem facing the growth of unemployment among the youth in Nigeria today could be identified among the following problems; political thuggery, militancy, restiveness, and other social vices which include; drugs abuse, prostitution, overpopulation, corruption, crime rate and poverty which are evident among the numerous problems that resulted from increase in unemployment.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to assess the socioeconomic effect of youth unemployment in Yola South Local Government Area of Adamawa State. The specific objectives are as follows:

- i.** To identify whether there is high rate of poverty as a result of unemployment in Yola South local government Area.
- ii.** To identify whether unemployment occur as a result of overpopulation in Yola South local government Area.
- iii.** To ascertain whether the rate of crime exist as a result of unemployment in Yola South local government Area.
- iv.** To identify whether unemployment lead to drug abuse in Yola South local government Area.

Literature Review:

2.1 Concept of Unemployment

Unemployment is one of the developmental problems that face every developing country, economy in the 21st century. International statistics portray that industrial and service workers living in developing region account for about two-thirds of the unemployed (Patternson et al, 2006).

The Nigeria economy since the attainment of political independent in 1960 has undergone fundamental structural changes. The domestic structural shifts have however not resulted in any significant and sustainable economic growth and development. Available data shows that the Nigerian economy grows relatively in the greater part of the 1970s with respect to the oil boom encouraged wasteful expenditures in the public sector dislocation of the employment factor and also distorted the revenue vases for policy planning. This among many other crisis resulted in the introduction of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986 and the current economic returns. i.e care collective if the economic structural returns is the total restructuring of the Nigerian economy in the face of population explosion (Douglason et al, 2006).

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However, these economic and financial structural reforms put in place have not yielded significant results. In the light of this, this research work seek to economic how a major macroeconomic variable unemployment could be reduced through the informal sector which is a recent global issue targeted at empowering people towards being self-productive and independent (Akintoye, 2006).

We shall consider the key concepts in our research work, unemployment in Nigeria. In previous and recent times role of informal sector as a militating factor, the role of the micro-finance institutions and other relevant stakeholders in meeting the needs of the informal sector, while we also recommend how the informal sector can be activated in order to reduce unemployment in Nigeria which will invariably result in reducing poverty, improved standard of living, improved productivity and overalls improvement in economic performance among other benefits.

Unemployment alone does not make for economic development. Neither does it refer the economic development in its broad sense. What is unemployment then all about? According to Briggs (1973), unemployment is the difference between the number of labour employed at current rates and working conditions and the amount of labour not hired at these levels. However, Gbosi (2006), define unemployment as situation in which people are willing to work at the prevailing wage rate unable to find jobs. The implication of the definition by Gbosi is that everyone who is not being counted as part of the unemployed labour force, in order to avoid over estimation of the official rate of unemployment.

In recent times, the definition of unemployment by the international labour organization (ILO) is said to be more encompassing the unemployed is a member of the economically active population who have lost their jobs and those who have voluntarily left work (World Bank, 1998). The application of the definition across countries has been faulted especially for the purpose of comparison and policy formulated as countries characteristics are not the same in their commitment to resolving unemployment problems. More so, the preponderance of housewives who passes the ability and willingness to work, the definition of the age bracket all stands as the limitations to the definition by ILO (Douglason et al, 2006).

2.2 Review of theoretical literature

According to the (Financial Standard of 11th June 2009), the disclosure in the recent report log the national directorate of employment (NDE) Which put the number of Nigerian graduates as completely the compulsory national youth service corps (NYSC) within the last five years but has remained unemployed at over 200,000 is appalling. Considering that, this figure does not include those who did not enjoy tertiary education during the period but are equally unemployed, the situation demands immediate action by government at all levels. Unemployment retards human development and breeds poverty which in turn leads to low level of consumptions and income. The unrelenting social upheavals in the form of increasing crime wave and insecurity in the country are the unfortunate consequences of high unemployment rate. A recent report by the international labour organization (ILO) equally identify unemployment as the root causes of the growing rate of anti-social activities by the youths or young people usually create a sense of vulnerability, uselessness and idleness which in turn heightens the attraction of illegal activities. Conversely reduce unemployment rate will bring about improved human development and reduce poverty. It will also reduce crime and insecurity and enthrone an enabling and conducive environment that will attract the foreign industries into the country. It is worrying that despite vast human and material resources naturally bestowed on the country, gross mismanagement, profligate spending, poor leadership and corruption by the public

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officials have not allowed economic benefits and employments generation to the citizenry. No nation can effectively pursue development goal without mobilizing its youth behind such national endeavor. In fact, that is why youth development is the focus on national policy. Apart from their role in national defense, the youth also constitute a significant proportion of the country voting population; they play active roles in mobilizing their nations to confront the challenges of changes.

The worsening harsh economic climate does not help the situation either. With many industries folding up and government job becoming limited day by day, the unemployment situation is getting rapidly worse. Face with uncertain future and despair the youth are left at the mere of generous temptation including political thuggery, assassination and armed robbery to survive by hook or crook.

Combating unemployment is one of the grimmest challenges facing Nigeria current democratic order undoubtedly. Because no part of Nigeria should pretend that it is not feeling the impact of unemployment

Efforts made at combating unemployment one of the steps taken by the Nigeria government to reduce the problem of unemployment in the country was the establishment of the national directorate of employment (NDE) which was promptly and effectively by designing and implementing innovative programmes which are directed towards the provision of training opportunities through the graduate and management support services to graduate formers and small scale entrepreneurs. The objective of NDE spanned across the following programmes: **i.** Agricultural development programmes.

ii. Youth development and vocational skills development programmes.

iii. Special public works.

iv. Small scale industries and graduate employment programmes.

The aim of the agricultural programmes is to generate employment for graduates, nongraduates and school leavers in the agricultural sector with emphasis on self employment in agricultural production and marketing. The programmes are monitored by team of agricultural professionals in the agricultural department of the directorate. However, factor which include inadequate funding and let release of funds from the federal account others have imperiled the effectiveness of the NDE agricultural programme (Ogunlela Y, I. 2012).

The national economic employment and development strategy (NEEDS) was also introduced in March 2004, in order to confront the various macro-economic imbalances, social challenges and structural problems in the Nigeria economy.

One of the principal goals is to build a modern Nigeria that maximizes the potentials of every citizen so as to become the largest and the strongest African economy, and a force to be reckoned with in the world. To achieved this goal, NEEDS as a development strategy anchored on the private sector is to engineer wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction, however, NEEDS to achieved it objectives there is need to design many integrated programmes that can generate employment for women and youth to enhance growth and development (Adebayo and Ogimrinalo 2006) other programmes of Babangida administration and the present millennium development goals (MDGS) programmes are programmes that put in place to help combat the issue of poverty and other social upheaval as a result of unemployment in the country (Nigeria).

2.3 Causes of youth unemployment

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According to Alanana (2003), Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010), unemployment in Nigeria is a consequence of several factors. One significant factor is that of population growth. Nigeria has continued to experience high rate of population growth. The increasing population growth has produced an out whelming in rapid growth of labour which is outstripping the supply of jobs.

Related to the rapid population growth is the massive rural-urban migration by the young people.

Accordingly the rapid population growth degree of geographical mobility of youth in Africa in the form of rural urban migration has been influencing youth employment. In Nigeria, youth migrate to the cities more than other immigrants. But unfortunately, job opportunities in Nigeria cities are very limited. Thus, the urbanization rate of the youth has continued to create unemployment. Another factor is the lack of employable skills due to inappropriate school curricula. Analysts have argued that in Nigeria generally, the skill that job seekers possess do not match the needs and demands of employers (Adofu I,Ocheja A (2013) the education system in Nigeria, with its liberal bias, indeed, over supplies the labour market with graduates that do not possess the skills needed by employer. Many graduate in Nigeria lack entrepreneurial skills to facilitate self-employment.

Another factor is the perception of policy makers and the youth themselves about employment. To policy makers and the youth, employment means a job. With salary and working for someone else. It is this perception that has continued to influence the institutions in Nigeria that provide skills and training programmes are generally tailored towards preparing young people for formal sectors jobs. But because these jobs do not exist there is often a mismatch between the skills possessed by the job seekers and the available jobs. Recently there has been a strong recognition among policy makers in Nigeria that the absence of artisanal and vocational skills has been responsible for youth unemployment.

3.0 Source of Data Collection

The source of data used for the purpose of this research is both primary and secondary sources. Under the primary data or source of data, some structured questionnaire administration of which shall be administered to some unemployed youths only at random. However, the questionnaire will provide the information relating to certain variable in respect to unemployment. While the secondary source will be drawn from documents on unemployment journals, textbooks, newspapers, etc.

3.1 Population of the Study

For the purpose of this study, the research will administer questionnaires to the teeming youths of Yola South local government of Adamawa state aged between 26-35years. The population consists of a total number of 800 youths of Yola South local government.

3.2 Method of Data Analysis

In analyzing the data collected from the selected sample, the researcher used table, percentage distribution method and descriptive analysis to test questionnaires and present the collected data.

An orderly presentation of information gathered indicating the relationship between variables is done by the use of tables which are appropriate for easy presentation of data and comparison of two or more variables as well as for easy interpretation or analysis of data.

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Chi-square will be used as a statistical tool to assist the researcher in evaluating the probability of obtaining differences between the actual (observed) frequencies and the expected frequencies. Finally, chi-square will be used as a basis for testing the null hypothesis against the alternative hypothesis.

The formula for chi-square statistics is denoted by:

$$X^2 = \sum (F_o - F_e)^2$$

F_e

Where;

X^2 = Critical value

F_o = Observed frequency

F_e = Expected frequency

\sum = Summation

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis

In this section, simple percentage test would be used in the analysis of data. The data would be analysed based on the number of the result obtained from questionnaire.

Lastly, the section will interpret the result of the hypothesis to be tested. The test of the hypothesis will be carried out using the Chi-square technique.

Section A

Table 4.1a: Gender

Variable	Response	Percentage (%)
Male	300	60%
Female	200	40%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The table below shows that there are 300 (60%) of male youths and 200 (40%) female. This implies that male is administered than female in Yola South local government area of Adamawa state.

Table 4.2a: Age distribution

Age	Response	Percentage (%)
26-30	300	50%
31-35	150	30%
36-40	50	20%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

From the above table one can clearly see that the youths with the age distribution ranging from 26-30 have the highest percentage 50%, 31-35 years have 30%, and followed by age 36-40 that responded are 30%.

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Table 4.3a: Education

Variable	Response	Percentage (%)
SSCE	100	20%
ND/HND	140	28%
B.Sc.	250	50%
M.Sc.	10	2%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The table below depicts that most youths in Yola South local government area of Adamawa state educational background is B.Sc. representing 50% of the respondents, followed by ND/HND 28%, 20% SSCE and 10% of the responders possess M.Sc degree.

Table 4.4a: Marital Status

Variable	Response	Percentage (%)
Single	300	60%
Married	150	30%
Divorced	50	10%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The table shows that 300 respondents representing 60% are single, while married and divorced are 30% and 10% respectively.

Section B

Table 4.1b: Are their Unemployed youths in Yola South Local government Area?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	400	80%
No	100	20%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The above indicate that 400 (80%) people responded that youth unemployment in Yola South local government area while 100 (20%) responded that there are no youth unemployed in the area.

Table 4.2b: Are there unemployed youth effected by poverty?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	450	90%
No	50	10%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

From the table above 450 respondents representing 90% are of the opinion that youths unemployment leads to poverty in Yola South Local government area, while 10% of the respondents share contrary view.

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Table 4.3b: How would you assess the effects of poverty on the unemployed youth in Yola South local government?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Favourable	100	20%
Unfavorable	350	70%
No Effect	50	10%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

From the table above 350 representing 70% respondents opined that unemployment has unfavourable effect on the youth in Yola South local government area.

Table 4.4b: Who are the highest population group in Yola South local government?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Youths	300	60%
Adults	200	40%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

From the above table it was revealed that 200 responses (40%) are of the view that adults have the highest population in Yola South local government area. While 300 respondents (60%) are of the opinion that youths forms the highest population group.

Table 4.5b: Does over population increase poverty level among your youth?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	400	80%
No	100	20%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The table above shown that 400 people (80%) responded that over population increase poverty among youths while 100 (20%) said that it does not.

Table 4.6b: What is the effect of overpopulation on unemployed youths in the area?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Positive	150	30%
Negative	350	70%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

From the table above 350 people representing 70% said that over-population bestows negative effects on unemployed youths.

Table 4.7b: Does youths in Yola South local government involve in criminal act?

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Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	400	80%
No	100	20%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2015

The table above depicts that 400 respondents are of the opinion that youths in Yola South involved in criminal acts. This means that they engaged themselves to such acts because of unemployment.

Table 4.8b: Do over population increase poverty level among your youth?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Rapidly	300	60%
Average	150	30%
Slowly	50	10%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The table above revealed that overpopulation leads to increase poverty level in Yola South as opined by 300 respondents representing 60%.

Table 4.9b: How can youth unemployment be minimized to reduced crime rate in Yola South?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Through youth empowerment programmes	200	40%
Establishing industries	200	40%
Provision of loan facilities	100	20%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The above table shows that youth empowerment and creation of industries will reduce unemployment and crime rate with responses of 200 respondents (40%) each respectively, while 100 (20%) are of the view that provision of loan facilities is the way to reduce crime rate.

Table 4.10b: Are the youth in Yola South involved in drug abuse?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	400	80%
No	100	20%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The table depicts that 400 people representing 80% said that youths in Yola South engages in drug abuse activities while 100 (20%) said they do not.

Table 4.11b: Does the drug abuse activities come as a result of poverty and unemployment?

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Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	400	80%
No	100	20%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The result from the table indicates that drug abuse activities are carried out by youth in Yola South as a result unemployment and high rate of poverty in the area. This is affirmed by 400 (80%) of the respondents, while 100(20%) give contrary opinion.

Table 4.12b: Is there a significant relationship between unemployment and socioeconomic development in Nigeria?

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	350	70%
No	150	30%
Total	500	100%

Source: field survey 2018

The table indicate that there is need for employment to enhance socio-economic development since 350 respondents out of 500 disagree that there is no significant relationship between unemployment and socio-economic development in Nigeria, though 150 out of 500 were in there contrary opinion.

4.1 Data Interpretation

Here, the researcher intend to test his hypothesis and interprets the result appropriately and draw a conclusion.

Decision Rule $df = (R-1)(c-1)$ From table above

$C=3, R= 2$

Therefore, $df = (3-1) (2-1)$

$= 2 \times 1 \text{ df} = 2$

The decision rule is that we will accept that null hypothesis (H_0) when the calculated value (X^2) is greater than the critical a table value (X^2)

4.2 Testing of Hypothesis

Tables 4.2b, 4.7b and 4.10b were used below related to the research hypothesis; the table value.

Table 4.2.1: Observed frequency table

Variable	Q2	Q7	Q10	Total
Yes	400	450	350	1200
No	100	50	150	300
Total	500	500	500	1500

Yes (Mean) = $\frac{400 + 450 + 350}{3} = 400$

No (Mean) = $\frac{100 + 50 + 150}{3} = 100$

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Table 4.2.2: Expected frequency table

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Variable	Q2	Q7	Q10	Total
Yes	400	400	400	1200
No	100	100	100	300
Total	500	500	500	1500

Table 4.2.3: Chi-square table

O	E	O – E	(O – E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
400	400	0	0	0
450	400	50	250	0.625
350	400	-50	250	0.625
100	100	0	0	0
50	100	-50	250	2.5
150	100	50	250	6.250

Interpretation of the above result obtained from the above table, are calculated chi-square value is given as 6.250, below the critical table value which is =7.772

Therefore, my decision is rejected the Null hypothesis, and accept the alternative hypothesis that say there is significant relationship between the socio-economic development and unemployment in Nigeria.

4.3 Research Findings

From the above analysis, the following findings are made:

- i. The researcher discovers that there exist a high number of unemployed youths in Yola South local government area of Adamawa state.
- ii. The study also revealed that unemployment results to poverty in Yola South.
- iii. The research work found out that there is unfavorable effect of unemployment on the unemployed youths in Yola South local government area.
- iv. It also indicates that unemployment lead to drug abuse in the area of Yola South local government.
- v. That also, increase in population leads to unemployment and poverty rate in the area of Yola South local government.
- vi. That when youths are empowered, industries are created it will go a long way in reducing the unemployment in Yola South local government and in Nigeria at large.

5.1 Conclusion

Employment is a fundamental tool that can yield better result on the economic development of a nation, if its principle and implementation is strictly adhered to when resources are employed; it is advised that they should be used effectively and efficiently in a better way. In general, the national government, employment bodies and other private organizations need to tackle all necessary actions and steps which are possible to ensure effective employment of the nation’s resources. This will in turn aid to help solve other societal problems that are attributed to unemployment, such as criminal activities, drug abuse, etc.

5.2 Recommendations

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Unemployment is as old as the existence of human beings in social forms. As old as it is, there remains as to what constitute it within any social set up. After carrying out this research work one is compelled to recommend that the following steps should be put in place in order to achieve its employment aims and objectives;

National youth empowerment and vocational skill development programme should be redesigned for youths in reorganization of the facts that over 70% of the unemployed productive and marketable skills.

The most suitable way to salvage this problem of unemployment is to return the economy back to status like this can only be achieved by the effort of government empowerment programmes of the youths at large.

Secondly, should provide small scale industries and enabling environment for private sector to establish industries in order to employ the teeming youths in the country.

Lastly, policy makers should intensify sensitization on the dangers of drugs abuse to human life.

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